

COVERAGE OF ENVIRONMENTAL ISSUES IN THE PRESS

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Annotation: This article examines the role of the press in covering environmental issues and its significance in increasing public awareness and responsibility towards ecological challenges. The study emphasizes methods used by media, such as various journalistic genres and visual tools, to deliver environmental information effectively. Additionally, it discusses the unique aspects of reporting on specific environmental problems in Uzbekistan, such as the Aral Sea crisis and air pollution, and the impact of the press in shaping ecological awareness and responsibility.

Key words: Environmental journalism, press coverage, ecological awareness, environmental responsibility, Uzbekistan, Aral Sea crisis, air pollution, media influence, social responsibility.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada matbuotning ekologik masalalarni yoritishdagi roli va uning jamoatchilikda ekologik xabardorlik hamda mas'uliyatni oshirishdagi ahamiyati o'rganiladi. Maqolada ommaviy axborot vositalarida qo'llaniladigan turli jurnalistik janrlar va vizual vositalar orqali ekologik axborotni samarali yetkazish usullari ta'kidlanadi. Shuningdek, O'zbekistondagi Orol dengizi inqirozi, havo ifloslanishi kabi muayyan ekologik muammolarni yoritishning o'ziga xos jihatlari hamda matbuotning ekologik ong va mas'uliyatni shakllantirishdagi ta'siri muhokama qilinadi.

Tayanch so'zlar: Ekologik jurnalistika, matbuot yoritishi, ekologik xabardorlik, ekologik mas'uliyat, O'zbekiston, Orol dengizi inqirozi, havo ifloslanishi, OAV ta'siri, ijtimoiy mas'uliyat.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается роль прессы в освещении экологических проблем, анализируется ее значимость в повышении

осведомленности и ответственности общества перед экологическими вызовами. Особое внимание уделяется методам, используемым в СМИ, таким как различные журналистские жанры и визуальные инструменты, для эффективной передачи экологической информации. Также обсуждается влияние прессы на формирование экологического сознания и ответственности населения с акцентом на специфические экологические проблемы в Узбекистане, такие как кризис Аральского моря и загрязнение воздуха.

Ключевые слова: Экологическая журналистика, освещение прессы, экологическая осведомленность, экологическая ответственность, Узбекистан, кризис Аральского моря, загрязнение воздуха, влияние СМИ, социальная ответственность.

Introduction

Relevance of the topic: The global increase in environmental issues and the necessity of protecting the environment.

Research objective: To analyze how environmental issues are covered in the press and the impact of this coverage on societal attitudes towards ecosystems.

Methodology : This study is based on the analysis of newspapers, magazines, and online publications, along with surveys and interviews with experts [1].

1– picture [2].

Main content

The role of environmental topics in the press.

- The importance of environmental issues and the need for their coverage in the press.

- Information policies on environmental topics globally and in Uzbekistan.

- The main tasks of media in covering environmental issues.

Methods of covering environmental topics in the press.

- Journalistic genres: The role of genres such as articles, reports, interviews, analytical articles, and infographics in covering environmental topics.

- Information delivery techniques: Conveying reliable information through facts and figures; attracting attention to environmental issues with photos, videos, and graphics.

- Role of social media in environmental reporting: Reaching a broader audience through blogs and social networks [3].

The role of the press in shaping environmental awareness and responsibility.

- The press's role in increasing environmental awareness and responsibility in society.

- Changing public attitudes towards the environment through regular coverage of environmental topics.

- Inspiring interest in solving environmental problems and encouraging active participation among readers.

Unique aspects of covering environmental issues in Uzbekistan's press.

- Uzbekistan's environmental issues: the Aral Sea, air pollution, water scarcity.

2 – picture. Between 1989 and 2014 [4].

- Specific features and challenges of environmental topics in Uzbek media.

- The importance of covering environmental problems through collaboration with local and international environmental organizations.

Pros and cons of environmental coverage.

- Positive aspects: Raising mass awareness about environmental issues, monitoring ecological changes, and presenting them to readers.

-Negative aspects: In some cases, superficial or incorrect coverage of environmental issues, focusing solely on criticism, which may create a negative atmosphere [5].

Conclusion

The importance and need for comprehensive and systematic coverage of environmental issues in the press.

Recommendations: To improve the effectiveness of environmental coverage, journalists should enhance their skills, develop specialized courses, and use new media technologies in environmental reporting.

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